

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

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ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

**Deliverable 1.1. Implementation of the ARICE
Operational Liaison Panel (OLP) with ToR**

Submission of Deliverable

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Deliverable No. 1.1.

Implementation of the ARICE Operational Liaison Panel (OLP) with ToR.

Abstract

In order to fulfil the objectives of ARICE, the project implements three liaison panels:

The Operational Liaison Panel (OLP), the Industry Liaison Panel (ILP) and the Scientific Liaison Panel (SLP).

This deliverable resumes the implementation of the Operational Liaison Panel and the Terms of Reference the members have agreed upon.

1. Introduction

In the frame of WP1, the project ARICE aims at improving the coordination of the available heavy icebreakers, the ice-strengthened RVs and the ice-classified RVs across Europe. It aims at bringing ship operators and scientific communities together to jointly discuss, plan, and implement collaboration and interaction, aiming at better scientific and logistic coordination of all European Arctic polar research vessels (PRVs). Better networking and coordination of PRVs will result in an increase of the urgently needed ship-time for Arctic marine research. This will also lead to a more cost-effective use of the research fleet, as research needs can then be matched better with the choice of vessels, contributing to increased Arctic knowledge and data sharing. The harmonisation of the research fleet will also lead to a decrease of carbon footprints in the Arctic.

Thus, it is imperative for ARICE to network with the operators of PRVs to bring solutions forward to improve the accessibility of research vessels in the Arctic Ocean.

The Operational Liaison Panel has been initiated with the operators of the six ARICE research icebreakers. In addition, the operators of the ice-strengthened vessels RV Dana (Denmark), RV Aranda (Finland) and BIO Hespérides (Spain) indicated their interest to cooperate with ARICE. They have been included in the OLP as well.

Members of the Operational Liaison Panel at the time this deliverable is submitted (November 2018):

Name	Institution	Country	PRV name
Katarina Gardfeldt	SPRS	Sweden	IB Oden
Marius Hirsekorn	AWI	Germany	PRV Polarstern
John Guldahl	NPI	Norway	RV Kronprins Haakon
Alexandre Forest	Amundsen Science	Canada	CCGS Amundsen
Doug Baird	UAF	USA	RV Sikuliaq
Randolph Sliester	NERC-BAS	UK	RV Sir David Attenborough
Juha Flinkman	Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE)	Finland	RV Aranda
Dennis Libsjerg	DTU-Aqua	Denmark	RV Dana
Miguel Angel Ojeda	UTM-CSIC	Spain	BIO Hespérides

2. ARICE Operational Liaison Panel terms of reference

General

The European project ARICE “Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium” was launched on the first of January 2018, bringing together a team of 15 partners from 13 different countries from Europe, USA and Canada. The main objective of this four-year project is to improve the capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

The Operational Liaison Panel will have an important role in helping ARICE to achieve its aim of improving the coordination of European PRVs, by networking the European icebreakers and ice-classified vessels with the objective of improving their coordination and avoiding duplication of efforts.

MEMBERSHIP

The Operational Liaison Panel (OLP) is comprised of operators of European Polar Research Vessels (PRVs) and international icebreakers. The members of the OLP are identified by WP1 and appointed by the General Assembly of ARICE. The Chair of the OLP will be elected from the panel and recommended to the General Assembly for approval.

OLP members will be appointed to ARICE for the full duration of the project.

Purpose

The purpose of the OLP is to help ARICE in its task of improving the coordination of European Polar Research Vessels (icebreakers and ice-classified vessels) and will have a key role in the harmonisation of the Arctic fleet.

Duties of the OLP

- Explore their specific interests and potentials to make commitments to a common European network of PRVs.
- Work towards reaching an agreement on implementing new ways of cooperation between institutes operating PRVs.
- Make use of experiences from other initiatives for pooling and harmonisation of resources of costly research infrastructures (for example the Ocean Facilities Exchange Group, OFEG).
- Some members of the OLP are also operators of the ARICE research icebreakers. This subgroup of the OLP will have a central role in the logistic evaluation of scientifically excellent proposals.

Communication channels

A member of the ARICE Management Team will be the principal recipient of the OLP's communications and advice who will then report to the ARICE Steering Board. Feedback will be captured at OLP meetings.

Meetings

The Chair of the OLP will take part at the annual ARICE General Assembly meetings to follow the progress of the project as a link with the operators of polar research vessels.

The members of the OLP are expected to participate at networking workshops for researchers and PRV operators. The workshops will be held most likely in conjunction to the yearly Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) meetings, which are always taking place at the Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW).

Travelling expenses for the OLP meetings will be covered by the ARICE consortium.

NB: This document has been approved by all the OLP members.